

Is Ritual a Useful Resource? Instrumental and Non-Instrumental Interpretations of Ritual Action

JORG KUSTERMANS
University of Antwerp, Belgium

This paper seeks to unsettle instrumental interpretations of ritual action, which also frame the current special issue. The instrumental interpretation of ritual action has political actors take deliberate recourse to ritual practices in order to accomplish various political ambitions. In spite of its obvious interpretive merit, the instrumental interpretation of ritual action loses its self-evidence when read in light of the contested history of ritual theory. Longstanding arguments about auto-telicity, universal participation, and ritual instinct suggest the plausibility of a non-instrumental interpretation of ritual action. Through the concepts of agency and protagonism, this paper seeks to explicate both alternatives and assesses their merit in a political context through a case study of Willy Brandt's iconic genuflection in Warsaw.

Este artículo tiene como objetivo desestabilizar las interpretaciones instrumentales de la acción ritual, las cuales, también, enmarcan el número especial actual. La interpretación instrumental de la acción ritual considera que los actores políticos recurren de forma deliberada a prácticas rituales con el fin de cumplir diversas ambiciones políticas. A pesar de su evidente valor interpretativo, la interpretación instrumental de la acción ritual deja de resultar obvia cuando se lee a la luz de la controvertida historia de la teoría del ritual. Los prolongados debates sobre el autotelismo, así como la participación universal y el instinto ritual sugieren la plausibilidad de una interpretación no instrumental de la acción ritual. Este artículo utiliza los conceptos de agencia y protagonismo con el fin de explicar ambas alternativas y analiza su valor en un contexto político. Para ello, utilizamos un estudio de caso de la icónica genuflexión de Willy Brandt en Varsovia.

Cet article vise à ébranler les interprétations instrumentales de l'action rituelle, qui cadrent aussi ce numéro spécial. L'interprétation instrumentale de l'action rituelle suppose que les acteurs politiques aient délibérément recours aux pratiques rituelles afin de réaliser différentes ambitions politiques. En dépit de son mérite interprétatif évident, l'interprétation instrumentale de l'action rituelle perd son évidence si on la lit à la lumière de l'histoire contestée de la théorie rituelle. Des arguments de longue date quant à l'autotélicité, la participation universelle et l'instinct rituel indiquent la plausibilité d'une interprétation non instrumentale de l'action rituelle. Par le biais des concepts d'agence et de protagonisme, cet article vise à expliciter les deux alternatives et évalue leur mérite dans un contexte politique grâce à une étude de cas de la genuflection emblématique de Willy Brandt à Varsovie.

Introduction

In her introductory article to this special issue, Maria Mälksoo defends the importance of paying attention to rituals in world politics by insisting that they have causal impact. She adopts what she calls a “performative approach to ritual,” which assumes that “rituals bring things about (rather than just bringing things to light)” (Mälksoo 2026: this issue; Robbins 2016).¹ Stated in these terms, this can hardly be wrong. Anything that happens in the world is bound to have an impact on the world. When a butterfly flaps its wings, for instance, there will be a causal impact on the world, however insignificant: air is moved. In the same way, when a world-political ritual is performed, there will always be some kind of causal impact: say, a short news item being created and diffused.

However, this is not the extent of Mälksoo's argument. We ought to care about the performance of rituals, she maintains, because they have a significant impact on the world. This is a view that appears to be widely shared. Oren and

Solomon (2015: 316), for instance, explain that the ritualized chanting of the “utterance “weapons of mass destruction” ultimately produced the grave Iraqi threat that it ostensibly described” and thus cleared the way for the military invasion of the country and all that followed in its wake. Nicole Wenger's (2021: 2) interpretation of the significance of military commemoration rituals offers another example. She argues that “it is through rituals [...] that militarism as an ideology is reified” and lodged into a polity's social structure. In an early application of ritual theory in our field, Barkawi (2017) argued that one cannot understand why imperial subjects agreed to sacrifice their lives in imperial armies if one does not take into account the centrality of collective rituals in military organizations, imperial or otherwise. Finally, consider Koschut's (2024) perceptive rendering of American president Trump's refusal to perform the ritual of publicly committing to Article 5 during his first attendance of a NATO summit in 2017. He maintains that Trump's ritual refusal weakened the bonds of the NATO security community and, as a consequence, jeopardized the dependable expectation of peaceful change. Deliberate refusal being a type of performance (Camp 2019; compare Bettiza and Lewis 2020), this shows again how world-political ritual is taken to be worthy of study because it has a significant impact on the world. World-political rituals matter, so the argument goes, because they can “bring things about.” They can bring about things of

*Corresponding author: University of Antwerp, Belgium. Email: jorg.kustermans@uantwerpen.be

¹For valuable feedback on an earlier draft of this article I would like to thank two anonymous reviewers, the editors of GSQ, Maria Mälksoo, Iver Neumann, Dorothy Noyes, Julia Costa Lopez, Benjamin Herborth, Guilherme Marques Pedro, and my colleagues in the research group International Politics at the University of Antwerp.

Kustermans, Jorg (2026) Is Ritual a Useful Resource? Instrumental and Non-Instrumental Interpretations of Ritual Action. *Global Studies Quarterly*, <https://doi.org/10.1093/isagsq/ksag013>

© The Author(s) 2026. Published by Oxford University Press on behalf of the International Studies Association. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

significance, even when at first glance they appear “insignificant” (Aalberts et al. 2020: 244).

But neither does this formulation—to wit: that the performance of ritual has a *significant* impact on the world—capture the full extent of Mälksoo’s argument. She further insists that world-political actors know the performance of ritual to have significant impact and stage rituals in order to accomplish said impact. She states that:

Ritual can be a politically handy tool [...]. Being manipulatable and dramatizable, rituals do political work (such as generating a sense of community and solidarity) and hence can serve as a useful resource in conducting politics. The performative power of rituals incentivizes the ritual “entrepreneurs” of international politics to ritualize for a reason: aspiring to create (at least) a momentary community along with transposing people to another time-space through ritual action. (Mälksoo 2026: this issue)

In this view, world-political actors intend the performance of ritual to have the effects that they accomplish. They use ritual performances (and ritual refusals) as an instrument. In the words of Baele and Balzacq (2022: 4): “leaders deploy [...] ritualized occasions.” If the causal significance of world-political rituals is widely accepted and often explicitly expressed by scholars of world-political ritual, this further “strategic” or “instrumentalist” twist is less commonly articulated with the same candor. Lucas Knotter’s (2021: 254) explanation of why *de facto* states persist in the ritualistic declaration of independence is a partial exception. He consistently presents their ritual performance as a means to an end, as deliberately serving a “purpose”: it is an “attempt to fuse” their performance with legal recognition; it is a means to “express an internal belief in redemption”; and it is taken to “bolster” a polity’s semblance of state community. In Knotter’s view, *de facto* states declare independence *in order to* fuse, express and bolster. While less plain than the quote from Mälksoo’s introductory paper, and also less explicit than Baele and Balzacq’s (2022) reference to leaders’ “deployment” of ritual occasions, this nonetheless reveals a rather overt instrumental conception of ritual action—of why people take recourse to ritual action. This assessment also applies to von Billerbeck’s (2020: 209) argument about how international organizations engage in self-legitimation. In this process, she maintains, “language, symbolism, and ritual are used to legitimate decisions and maintain belief systems in organizations” (also Hoffmann in Kustermans et al. 2022). Admittedly, the matter is more complicated in the arguments of Oren and Solomon (2015) and Wenger (2021), which put more emphasis on the possibility of rituals to entrap their participants affectively—in which case, rather than people using the ritual, the rituals appear to be using the people. People fall in step with the rhythm of the ritual chanting. They are swayed by the affective force of the ritual commemoration. But also here the story starts with this or that (set of) entrepreneur(s) initiating the chant or organizing the commemoration, and doing so with an outspoken political purpose in mind. When world-political entrepreneurs *use* ritual, that is, they *use* the people that join the ritual performance too. Barkawi (2017: 185) states the point plainly: “The point of ritual systems is [...] to dispose people toward acting in particular kinds of ways, those intended by ritual experts.”

This approach to theorizing ritual action makes a good deal of sense and may be said to conform with the habitus of world-political actors. It has the benefit of what Alfred Schutz (1962: 44) called interpretive “adequacy,” which he considered a criterion of good social science and defined as an interpretation’s “existential relevance to the [...] actors in the life-world” (Zijderveld 1972: 189). To the extent—and I think it is large—that political conduct is animated by a de-

sire to impose one’s preferred collective outcome (on others, on the world) and that political actors draw on whatever resources that they have access to in order to achieve that end (Bartolini 2018),² it is fitting that our attempts to incorporate the concept of ritual into our theoretical frameworks would reflect these characteristics of politics. In this view, premising these attempts on an instrumental conception of ritual action—whereby ritual features as one of the instruments in the toolkit of world-political actors—ensures their interpretive adequacy.

And yet I hesitate to leave it there. The approach makes sense but does not satisfy. The approach reminds me of the worry that the anthropologists Humprey and Laidlaw (1994: 125) expressed. A lot of ritual theory, they explained, is actually not theory of ritual at all, but theory of the phenomenon being ritualized. They give the example of “rites of passage.” In the wake of van Gennep’s (1909) early account and Turner’s (1979) theoretical elaboration of the concept, it is widely known that rites of passage have three stages: separation, a liminal period and reaggregation. This is empirically well-established and has been put to productive use in plenty of ritual-inflected scholarship (Thomassen 2009; Mälksoo 2012; Rumelili 2012; Horvath et al. 2015). According to Humprey and Laidlaw (1994: 125), however, the identification of these three stages says next to nothing about the distinctively ritual nature of ritual action. They make the very simple point that “rites of passage have three stages not because they are *rites* of passage, but because they are rites of *passage*.” Liminality tells us very little about ritualization *per se*, even though it tells us a lot about the nature and experience of transitions. In the same way, I cannot help but feel that an approach to ritual action in world politics that insists on the instrumental use of ritual performance by world-political actors serves mainly to reaffirm the political nature of the performance of world-political rituals, rather than clarify their distinctively ritual nature.

In light of these reservations, my purpose in this paper is to unsettle the instrumental approach to ritual action that frames the current special issue. I do so in four steps. First, through the concept of agency, I reconstruct in social-theoretical terms how an instrumental approach to ritual action envisions the use of ritual by political entrepreneurs and how they are taken to benefit from it. Second, I identify three entailments of thinking about *ritual as an instrument* and question their self-evidence by introducing three key ideas from the contested history of ritual theory: auto-telicity, universal participation and ritual instinct. Third, I develop an alternative, non-instrumental approach to ritual action through the concept of protagonism. Finally, in order to pre-empt the criticism that the notion of ritual protagonism lacks interpretive adequacy in the context of world politics, I briefly discuss Willy Brandt’s genuflection before the Memorial of the 1943 Warsaw Ghetto Uprising during a state visit to Poland. I juxtapose two interpretations of the event: a first that presents the German chancellor as a ritual agent and a second that presents him as a ritual protagonist. Given my purpose to unsettle the instrumental approach to ritual action, I emphasize the weaknesses of the first interpretation and highlight the interpretive value of the second interpretation.

²Note that legal frameworks and social taboos can put a limit on the resources that political actors have access too. In addition to material considerations, instrumental action is always constrained by social norms.

Agency: An Instrumental Approach to Ritual Action

In order to clarify how an instrumental understanding of ritual action works, I begin with a brief discussion of agency, because it is as (political) agents that ritual actors can most readily be assumed to use ritual as an instrument. To the extent that instrumental action is the preserve of agents (Schatzki 2025: 2), so is instrumentally performed ritual action. At its most basic, agency refers to “the capacity for effective and meaningful action” (Robb 2010: 515). People have agency when they can accomplish their goals. People have agency when they can define their own goals and have a fair chance to overcome the inevitable obstacles to the accomplishment of these goals (Epstein et al. 2018). Agency concerns “the individual’s ability to effect his or her will or intention” (Robb 2010: 496). For action to count as an expression of agency, it must be seen to result from and controlled by a person’s will or intention.

Although agency so defined may be a delusion, actors tend to think of themselves as agents and tend to assess their own and others’ conduct in terms of the agency that propelled it. Agency describes a phenomenological reality (Bayne 2008). Habermas (2007: 14) captured this well when he wrote that “as agents, we are convinced of the irreducible distinctiveness and causal effectiveness of our minds. We are certain that we act of our own accord and can make things happen in the world.” I would add that, as agents, we feel satisfaction when we manage to make things happen in the world and displeasure when we fail to make things happen in the world, when we fail to master the “effects and forces” that confront us in the world (Bamberg 2022). As agents, we have the ambition to make things happen in the world. The more we have the ambition to make things happen in the world, the more we become *political* agents. That is to say: the more we have the ambition to give shape to the world in which we ourselves and others try to make things happen, the more we become political agents. Political actors want to maximize their agency. They lust for mastery (Augustine 2013: 45). Their ambition is to achieve agency unhampered by constraints in the environment or by the agency of others.

The ambition for agency can be frustrated (Epstein et al. 2018), and so can *a fortiori* the ambition for mastery. Often a gap lies between “will and intention” and “will and intention having their effect.” As agents, in these moments of frustration but also preemptively, we have a whole “toolkit” of instruments available to try to skirt the obstacles that cause or could cause frustration (Swidler 1986). The availability of these instruments and resources varies from one person to the next. Some have ready access, others do not, at least not to all instruments. But these variations in access do not invalidate the more basic point that as agents, as people desiring to exercise agency, certainly as political agents lusting for mastery, we take recourse to a variety of resources to bridge the gap between intention and effect. Enter ritual action. Political actors take recourse to ritual action to amplify their agency. As Baele and Balzacq (2022: 4: emphasis added) write, “leaders deploy [. . .] ritualized occasions.” The metaphor is military in origin. Much in the way that leaders deploy troops, they deploy ritualized occasions too. The ambition would appear to be the same: either to achieve mastery (when deployed offensively) or to retain agency (when deployed defensively).

But how does recourse to ritual action amplify the agency of political actors? How, that is, do rituals staged and performed by political actors amplify their agency? For clarity’s sake, I will focus my attention on how ritual actions benefit powerful political actors, although the argument can rel-

atively easily be tweaked to apply to less powerful actors too (Farneth 2023)

At its most basic, ritual action enables and amplifies agency through orchestration. The powerful get to orchestrate ritual occasions, which they may do to self-serving effect. Self-serving orchestration works its effect through three mechanisms. First, the orchestration of ritual occasions involves the decoration of the environment and the self, with the intended effect of bedazzling other, less powerful participants and the audience. A beautiful carpet is laid out, a throne is sat on or an altar stood behind, a splendid crown or robe put on. In the process, the distance between those in power and those subject to power is increased, the distinction between them reified. Second, the orchestration of ritual occasions frequently involves the participation of the less powerful. They join the ritual occasion, whether from curiosity, because of a hoped-for benefit, including the opportunity to assert themselves during the encounter afforded by the ritual occasion (Kustermans 2021), or through compulsion. But when they do join the ritual occasion, they inevitably confirm the symbolic order that the ritual performance gives expression to, including their own subordination within that symbolic order. Writing about subjects’ participation in hegemonic rites, Bell (1992: 215) pointed at their thoroughly restrained scope for resistance. Although the subjects’ minds may be disengaged from the performance, and although this disengagement may result from a certain refusal of the symbolic order, “bowing or singing in unison imperceptibly schools the social body in the pleasures of and schemes for acting in accordance with assumptions that remain far from conscious or articulate.” The powerful orchestrate, the less powerful move and dance, they hum and sing to their tune. Over time, the moving, dancing, humming, and singing become second nature, the tune a source of pleasing familiarity. The powerful orchestrate and thereby get the less powerful to do and want what they want them to do and want. In the process, the powerful amplify their agency. The less powerful do not necessarily have their agency disabled, but the more powerful amplify their agency more. They gain in relative power.

In addition to the distinction-reifying decoration of the powerful self and the awe-inspiring decoration of the ritual environment, as well as the symbolic-order-confirming participation of the less powerful, the orchestration of ritual occasions amplifies the agency of those who orchestrate them by giving them pride of place during the ritual occasion, by giving them a platform from which to stage a captivating performance that, when successful, may cast a spell on their audience. If distinction-reifying decorations work their magic even without active engagement on the part of those decked out with the decorations—they may sit still on their throne, they may be hid behind a curtain—a skillful performance on their part—re-enacting this or that past event, delivering a charismatic discourse—nonetheless adds to the effect. Ritual occasions afford the powerful ample opportunity to project a particularly appealing image of themselves. “Ritual conventions,” in these situations, become the platform from which the powerful can stage their performance. Interestingly, in their assessments of these performances—within-ritual-occasions audiences will often put a premium on “authenticity.” Whereas the notion of ritual may be said to connote conformity, the notion of performance connotes authenticity (Alexander 2004; Baele and Balzacq 2022: 3), and has been argued to benefit from moments of transgression (Chowdhury and Duvall 2011). As such, it may be argued that adding a deliberately performative, a more or less bluntly transgressive element to ritual action, when confined to the

temporal and spatial boundaries of the ritual occasion, serves to shore up an appearance of mastery. In any case, when powerful political agents stage a ritual performance, there are various ways in which the enactment of the rite—although none of them failproof—should help consolidate their position of power and thus amplify their agency. On this basis, we are right to think that ritual is a useful resource.

Ritual as Instrument: Three Considerations from the Contested History of Ritual Theory

As explained in the previous section, the notion of ritual agency is premised on an instrumental understanding of human action, including ritual action. It presumes that actors use ritual (as an instrument) *in order to* achieve goals that lie beyond the moment of performance. As an instrument, ritual can be put to all kinds of purposes: its “*in order to*” is underdetermined. Political actors stage a ritual performance *in order to* strengthen communal solidarity, *in order to* consolidate or improve their position of power, *in order to* render their relations with others (and the Other) less tense. Another aspect of the instrumental conception of ritual action is that it assumes that ritual can be performed more or less competently and that its efficacy in achieving the variable ends towards which it is being put—solidarity, authority, and harmony—depends on the competence of the performance. The more virtuoso the performance, including the occasional ritual transgression, the likelier that the end that the ritual performance is meant to help attain will indeed be attained. And a final aspect of the instrumental conception of ritual action is that it implies interchangeability. While some particular instruments may be particularly fit for this or that particular task, it is rarely the case that some other instrument could not be used for the same purpose. One can eat sticky rice with either a fork, chop sticks, or one’s hands. In the same way, one can seek to establish one’s authority through either material generosity, rhetorical prowess, or ritual orchestration—or some combination thereof. When one conceives of ritual action as instrumental action, any particular ritual (but also ritual as such) appears as an instrument indeed, that is to say: as “something more or less exchangeable for other such instruments” (Schatzki 2010: 150).

To conceive of ritual action as instrumental action, I submit, is to accept these various conceptual entailments more or less explicitly. However, none of these implications is self-evident in light of the contested history of ritual theory. In what follows, therefore, I wish to unsettle the instrumental approach to ritual action through an engagement with a number of ideas from this contested history of ritual theory. In the next section, then, I will sketch an alternative approach that centers on the notion of ritual protagonism.

Entailment I: Ritual Action Serves a Purpose beyond Itself and beyond the Moment

This first and most central element of the instrumental understanding of ritual action is maybe the most difficult to unsettle. An important reason is that even when ritual action would be accepted not to be enacted for a purpose beyond enacting it, it could still be the case, and many would argue that it is in fact the case, that ritual serves a purpose. These purposes are typically conceptualized in terms of the “functions” of ritual. Schatzki (2010: 143) identifies five such functions in the literature: strengthening social solidarity, fostering group identity, resolving personal and social problems, reaffirming a groups’ moral principles, and/or symbol-

izing the central concepts that give meaning to people’s lives. Bellah (2005: 197) offers an alternative list: positioning ritual participants in society, giving them an identity relative to others, and proving them a social location. Ritual—especially collective ritual—is often assumed to perform these or similar functions; which is equally to say: ritual is often assumed to serve these or similar purposes that evidently lie beyond their very enactment.

The point is well-taken but gives neither necessary, nor exclusive support to the instrumental understanding of ritual action. After all, ritual activity could serve such purposes unwittingly. Their being served may well be a recurrent (though never quite secure) effect of ritual action, but that does not—in and of itself—make them the *intended* purpose of ritual action. They could be their intended effect, but they could also be a “side-effect” of ritual action (Staal 1979: 11). Ritual’s functions—as social theorists discern them—do not have to align with ritual actors’ reasons for—or their purposes in—enacting them. As also Schatzki (2010: 144) emphasizes: “functions [. . .] must be distinguished both from the ends people pursue in carrying out ceremonial and rituals actions and from the ends and purposes they attribute to their ceremonies and rituals.” They may coincide. They may not.

If this is agreed, this creates an important opening for the possibility that people enact rituals for non-instrumental reasons, for reasons that do not concern a purpose beyond the moment of enactment. There are at least three possibilities here. The first non-instrumental reason—although *reason* is admittedly not quite the right word to use—could be habit. When two acquaintances meet, they may shake hands out of sheer habit, without giving any thought to the gesture. They habitually greet each other with a ritual gesture. A second non-instrumental reason could be obligation. When two leaders of state meet in the context of a state visit, for instance, they are likely to shake hands too. However, their ritual gesture will not proceed unthinkingly as in the case of the encounter between two acquaintances. They know that their office entails that they must greet their foreign counterparts with due ceremony and so they shake hands at least in part out of a sense of obligation. As a result, a higher degree of solemnity is likely to inflect the ritual gesture—say, by having it last a touch longer. Admittedly, an instrumental concern with “agency” and “mastery” can easily creep into the enactment. This appears to have been the case when French President Macron refused to release American President Trump’s hand when they shook hands during their first encounter. Wong (2021: 359) maintains—plausibly—that “Macron’s behavior was intentional,” that he “employed the gesture to cast himself in an advantageous position” (compare Hillewaert 2016). But also in such case, the instrumental concern with agency must not erase the role of habit and obligation. The various reasons for action are not mutually exclusive. Instrumental considerations can always come to inflect otherwise non-instrumental activity. Performative elements (in the sense elaborated above), that is, can always be introduced into otherwise strictly ritual occasions. And vice versa.

A more radical type of non-instrumental reason for ritual action is so-called “auto-telicity” (Lopez-Frias 2020: 169–170; building on Aristotle’s *Nicomachean Ethics* 1.7,1097b34–1098a5). People engage in a certain activity for autotelic reasons when they do so for its own sake, when they do not pursue some external purpose by engaging in the activity (Csikszentmihalyi and Gilbert 1995: 7). When two adolescents meet, they may shake hands in an especially elaborate choreography. It is as if their hands dance. They shake hands out of neither habit nor obligation, but for the sheer enjoyment of shaking hands in this ceremonial fashion. Going through

the motions of the ceremonial handshake is their reason to shake hands. In the same way, taking into account the human penchant for commensality (in general) and ritual commensality (in particular) (Otto 2015: 205), one imagines that state banquets—the more ritualistic of diplomatic meals—retain an autotelic aspect for the diplomats who attend them.

In his account of Vedic ritual, the Dutch Indologist Staal (1979) radicalizes this auto-telic aspect of ritual action. He draws attention to the notion of *tyaga*, which he presents as a key concept in Vedic ritual theory and renders as the “renunciation of the fruits of the ritual acts.” He clarifies the idea with an example.

When the officiating priest, on behalf of the patron, makes the oblation into the fire for one of the gods, for example Agni, the Patron says: “this is for Agni, not for me.” (Staal 1979: 6)

Vedic ritual action, according to this interpretation, was not merely non-instrumental in orientation but was animated by a distinctly anti-instrumental spirit. Ritual action was conceptualized as a form of action that was not meant to further the interests of ritual actors or amplify their agency (“not for me”). From this and similar observations in various cultural traditions, Staal (1979: 14; emphasis added) ventures a general, of necessity speculative, theoretical hypothesis about the experiential origins of ritual activity that casts the emergence of ritual practices as a response to the ambivalent experience of human agency. He explains that he thinks

that man [*sic*] became aware of himself primarily as an agent. [...] Abandoning a sense of being pushed around, man [*sic*] made the discovery that he affected the outside world by engaging in activity – [but the exercise of agency turned out to be] a pursuit wrought with risk and danger. So he [*sic*] created a world of ritual or ideal activity, intrinsically successful and free from such contingencies. [...]

As said, this is a necessarily speculative proposition. What is more, the proposition appears to smuggle in strongly instrumental considerations in what Staal (1979: 7, 14) intends to be a discussion of the enactment of ritual “for its own sake,” of ritual as “perfect activity” that is “free from such contingencies” precisely because its enjoyment is immediate, because its enjoyment does not depend on the achievement of a further purpose or outcome. After all, if Staal’s argument holds that humankind “created a world of [auto-telic] ritual [...] activity” in order to alleviate the sense of “risk and danger” that the exercise of agency triggers, this amounts to a paradox. In Staal’s account, ritual activity simultaneously figures as instrumental and non-instrumental action; as a deliberate response to the ambivalent experience of agency and as being enacted for its own sake. Having said that, the paradox becomes less stark if one takes note of the fact that while the “instrumental” consideration is temporally situated in a speculative original moment and attributed to the theoretical figure of (hu)man(kind), the “non-instrumental” part of the argument presumably concerns the concrete enactment of particular ritual practices by actual people. Once established as “perfect activity,” and whatever its side-effects and latent societal functions, people may well engage in ritual action for its own sake. At the very least, it is an option that is available to them, and that ritual practices (like play and contemplation; Lopez Frías 2020) may be said to be particularly fit contexts for.

Entailment 2: The Efficacy of Ritual Action Depends on Competent Performance

To the extent that the above observations unsettled the self-evidence of the idea that ritual action serves a purpose be-

yond itself, they also diminish the significance of the second entailment, which holds that the efficacy of ritual action depends on competent performance. After all, if efficacy is not an intrinsic concern of ritual action, so is neither competent performance as a determinant of ritual efficacy. However, when instrumental considerations *do* inform or inflect ritual action, which I have acknowledged to be a regular occurrence, the actors enacting a particular rite will logically care about ritual efficacy and therefore care about competent performance too. They will care about getting it right so as to render their enactment of the rite as impactful as possible.

The point is well-taken and indicates again that a non-instrumental understanding of ritual action should not be developed to the exclusion of an instrumental understanding of the phenomenon. Having said that, the rich repertoire of ritual theory does include strong arguments to the effect that ritual practices are prone to foster an autotelic attitude among ritual actors. In this view, if ritual actors care about “getting it right” (Humphrey and Laidlaw 1994: 111), they do for the sake of getting the rite right, not in order to achieve a further purpose by getting the rite right. They care about competent performance as a good internal to the practice (MacIntyre 2007: ch. 14), not as a means to impress others and thereby get them to support whatever goal the enactment of the rite was meant to help attain. The (theoretical) characteristic of ritual practices that sustains this particular definition of competent performance is that of universal participation. In the recent history of ritual theory, Rappaport (1999: 135) was particularly adamant on this point. He insisted on the (again: theoretical) difference between ritual enactment and theatrical performance, arguing that “those present at a ritual constitute a congregation” and then explaining that

the defining relationship of the members of a congregation to the event for which they are present is *participation*. Those present at theatrical events include, on the one hand, *performers* and, on the other hand, *audiences*. [...] The defining characteristic of audience in contrast to performers on the one hand and congregation on the other is that they do not participate in the performance: they *watch* and they *listen*.

Obviously, the distinction between ritual events (without audience) and theatrical events (with audience) is not an absolute one. Originally ritual events (say, a church service which has a priest presiding and parishioners celebrating) can be observed by non-participants (say, tourists entering a church building during a service). Or participants in a rite can tune out of the solemnity of the event, lose focus, and begin to observe their fellow congregants from the outside. Alternatively, the actors on a theater stage may actively involve the audience in their performance so that it increasingly comes to resemble a ritual occasion. And there are many more ways to complicate the distinction (Baele and Balzacq 2022), which should be considered, I wish to emphasize, an ideal-typical one.

But still, I find it useful to draw the distinction because it clarifies the distinctive meaning of “competent performance” in an ideal-typically ritual context. The theoretical feature of universal participation, that is, has as a non-consequence that the impact of the enactment of a rite on non-participants becomes a non-issue. As Humphrey and Laidlaw (1994: 111) put it: “the question of what you need to do in order to create an affecting display [for an audience] can be separated from the question of what you need to do in order to get a ritual right.” The more an occasion leans to the side of an ideal-typical ritual event, the less likely that the concern with creating an affecting display will arise. This is so because during ritual events all who are present participate, as a result of which there is no audience to stage an affecting display

for. In order to get the ritual right, it suffices to perform the necessary gestures and utter the necessary words, however clumsily. It is precisely this elimination of the gaze of an audience, a gaze prone to combine hopeful anticipation with a touch of skepticism, which creates an enabling circumstance for ritual actors' unconcern with the amplification of their agency. The imagined, the presupposed absence of an audience eliminates a further element of contingency (Kessler 2016) and thereby creates a felicitous condition for the enactment of ritual as a form of "perfect activity." By curtailing the use of ritual as an instrument to sway an audience (in order get it to support causes external to the ritual activity), it creates a context fit for autotelic ritual enactment. A core idealtypical feature of ritual practices, that is, fosters an unconcern with affecting display and thereby diminishes actors' ability (and their inclination) to define competent performance as the ability to manipulate ritual performances for instrumental purposes.

Entailment 3: Ritual Action Is Interchangeable with Non-ritual Action.

The third entailment of the instrumental understanding of ritual action holds that, in the pursuit of the various ends that lie beyond the ritual enactment, ritual action is "more or less exchangeable for other [...] instruments" (Schatzki 2010: 150). On this account, the enactment of ritual does not hold intrinsic value, it is not an end-in-itself, but a *mere* means to an end, to be exchanged for some other instrument if that other instrument serves the purpose better.

It is worth noting that this is the view that informed so-called "evolutionist" interpretations that relegated ritual activity to a pre-modern past. In James Frazer's *The Golden Bough*, for instance, it was a key idea that premodern "man [*sic*] worshipping is first and foremost an actor. He *does* something to cause his gods to shine their countenances upon him [*sic*]. [...] When he moves, he acts out what he wants the gods to do for him [*sic*]" (Ackerman 1975: 124; emphasis in original). In the evolutionist view, human beings used ritual as an instrument in pre-modern times but abandoned the use of that instrument once modern science made better, more efficacious instruments available. Among the recent contributions to scholarship on rituals in international relations, Neumann's (2021: 192) argument about the diminishing importance of the exchange of diplomatic gifts as an instrument to stabilize inter-polity relations expresses a similar idea, except that he truly appreciates the contribution that ritual gift-exchange once made (while Frazer was prone to dismiss the premodern use of ritual as misguided).³ While diplomatic gifts once were *understood to be* crucial to the stabilization of inter-polity relations, they no longer are and, as a consequence, much fewer resources are invested in them. Diplomatic gift-exchange continues to be practiced, but, as the increasingly "fluffy" gifts indicate, now mostly as a "remnant." Others means are now available—not in the least a thick com-

plex of international institutions—that serve the same purpose more efficaciously.

Admittedly, most contributions to the growing body of scholarship on ritual in international relations does not adopt an evolutionist tack—whether in Frazer's original or in Neumann's attenuated form. They rather insist on the continuing relevance of ritual action. They suggest that ritual action is (and is bound to remain) a particularly useful instrument for certain purposes—for instance, in the establishment of authority by rendering a fundamentally nebulous and ambivalent phenomenon both palpable and palatable (Kustermans et al. 2022: 8–9); or in the creation of bonds of solidarity, including among the members of military units, by having them "keep together in time" during collective ritual practices like parade-ground drills (Barkawi 2017: 173–175; cf. McNeill 1996: 86–90). But still: a particularly useful instrument remains first and foremost an instrument. It remains a means to an end and cannot be assumed, *qua instrument*, to either enjoy intrinsic value or be non-exchangeable. Actors will seek to establish their authority or foster social cohesion in whatever way works. They may take recourse to ritual action. Or they may not.

However, while this argument about the interchangeability of ritual action is certainly plausible, it is not undisputed. Drawing from the rich repertoire of ritual theory again, there are two ways to counter it. The first would be to refer, as I did before, to a sense of (internalized) obligation that participants in a ritual event routinely attest to. Being a member of such or so society, or holding this or that office, it *goes without saying*, from the perspective of the persons involved, that one should and does enact the rites that come with membership in society or the occupation of office. While many rites will allow some leeway for how to enact them, including how much to commit emotionally, the very enactment of the rite is not—more precisely: not as long as the rite enjoys authoritative status—experienced as being subject to choice (Rappaport 1999: 123–124). To the extent that the sense of (internalized) obligation has phenomenological validity, and to the extent that (political) leaders share this sense, the idea of inter-changeability becomes less intuitive, and would appear to be bound by important scope conditions. One of these scope conditions could be that the sense of obligation exists only in non-pluralist societies, so that it might have applied in many societies of the past but it does no longer in most societies today (Alexander 2004). This would bring us back to a version of the evolutionist argument. However, a second way to counter the argument about inter-changeability avoids this concern by interpreting the recurrent and continuing enactment of ritual as the result of "ritual instinct" (de Lara 2003; Quack 2010; Wittgenstein 2018: 54). The notion expresses the anthropological intuition that ritualization—by which I mean here: the creation and enactment of ritual practices—comes naturally to people, both to individual people and to groups of people. This does not mean that people are compulsive ritualists, that they are constantly engaging in ritual action, but it does mean that they resort to ritual action, instinctively so, in certain situations. Schatzki (2010: 133) characterizes these situations as "impressive worldly phenomena." de Lara (2003: 119) describes them as "important or mysterious facts." Quack (2010: 180) settles for "significant phenomena." This notion that ritualization comes naturally to people when they are confronted with *situation that carry weight* appears to have informed and capture the gist of Arnold van Gennep's (1909) documentary account of rites of passage. If we accept Humphrey and Laidlaw's (1994: 125) argument that the identification of the

³In his remarks on Frazer's *The Golden Bough*, Wittgenstein (2018: 32) famously characterized Frazer's valuation of premodern ritual as a result of mistaken belief and the expression of stupidity, disagreeing strongly with that assessment on the basis that ritual efficacy was probably not the concern of premodern ritualists in the first place (see Quack 2010: 185). Neumann, however, shares with Frazer a concern with ritual efficacy, but assesses the reasonableness of premodern belief in ritual efficacy differently. One explanation for the different assessments of Frazer and Neumann, other than them writing in a different historical period, could be that Frazer focused on rites being performed to control the world, while Neumann focuses on a rite being performed in order to give shape to social relations (see also Quack 2010: 183).

three stages of rites of passage reflects the fact that they are rites of *passage*, but tells us next to nothing about the fact that they are *rites* of passage, what is left of van Gennep's argument (and amply documented in his account) is the fact that people experience transitions as significant moments and have systematically proceeded to ritualize them. They do so instinctively. And they could not do otherwise. At least in these and similarly weighty situations, which evolution cannot be expected to rid humanity of, ritual action does not appear to be inter-changeable with non-ritual action.

Protagonism: A Non-Instrumental Approach to Ritual Action

Dipping into the rich archives of ritual theory, I tried in the previous section to question the self-evidence of an instrumental understanding of ritual action. From these archives, I pulled up three ideas—auto-telicity, universal participation, and ritual instinct—that, each separately, unsettled the obviousness of a core element of instrumental interpretations of ritual action. The idea of auto-telicity unsettles the self-evidence of the argument that people ritualize for a reason. The idea of universal participation unsettles the self-evidence of the argument that competent performance is key to ritual efficacy. And the idea of ritual instinct unsettles the argument that ritual action is interchangeable with non-ritual action. Let me emphasize, though, that to unsettle the self-evidence of an argument does not add up to its invalidation, and that this was not the ambition either. The ambition was more modestly to create an opening for the development of an alternative, non-instrumental understanding of ritual action. The purpose of this section is to sketch such an alternative.

Whereas I developed the instrumental understanding of ritual action through the concept of *agency*, I will develop the non-instrumental alternative through the concept of *protagonism*. A protagonist is a character in a story. It is the lead character in a story, but the protagonist's pre-eminence is not my concern here. It is more important to insist that the actions of protagonists are not determined by the protagonist but by the author of the script and, in a still more fundamental sense, by the demands of the narrative structure of the script. When authors attribute intentions to their protagonists, they are in many ways predetermined by the kind of story which the author sets out to write—or that they find themselves to be writing. As the literary theorist Northrop Frye (1951: 104–105, 108–110) explained, a protagonist in a comedy grapples with different types of problems and is driven by a different set of desires than a protagonist in a romance, tragedy or satire. He referred to these various plot structures as “archetypal” and insisted that readers tend to value the quality of a particular novel or play to the extent that it corresponds to an archetype. The genius of an author, in this view, stems from their attunement to the “archetypal significance” of the stories that they are writing (Frye 1951: 103). *Everything happens as if* archetypes impress themselves on authors, inspiring them to write stories that have protagonists engage in archetypal fashion with archetypal situations.

Does this notion of (archetypal) protagonism travel from literature to ritual? One could argue that it does not travel well because, unlike narrative protagonists, ritual protagonists are flesh-and-blood people acting from their own initiative (whether by proper choice, out of habit or obligation, or from instinct). They are actual actors, not the literary representations of an actor. Ritual actors are, in this sense, the

authors of their own acts. But the objection does not quite discredit the notion of ritual protagonism. There are two reasons. The first reason is that while participants in ritual activity may be said to enact ritual practices from their own initiative, they cannot wholly determine their doings and sayings as they enact these ritual practices. Notwithstanding a certain leeway for improvisation, it is in the nature of ritual “acts and utterances [that they] are *not entirely* encoded by the performers” (Rappaport 1999: 24; emphasis added). As Humphrey and Laidlaw (1994: 99) explain: “In ritual you both are and are not the author of your acts.” The second reason is that, according to the archetypal account of (narrative) protagonism, authors are not wholly free to compose their stories either: they are animated by archetypes. Similarly, even if ritual protagonists are the authors of their own acts, they too may be said to be under the spell of a set of archetypes. Even when a person or group of people invents a new rite, that means, they will (have to) draw from deep-rooted, culturally grounded models or, in Frye's (1951) more radical version of the argument, fall back on even more deep-rooted, universally shared themes and forms of (embodied) expression. This will be the case both when actors ritualize for an instrumental reason and when they ritualize instinctively in response to a weighty situation. However, it seems reasonable to assume that instinctual ritualization will come with a stronger archetypal bent. After all, to the extent that instinctual ritualization happens in response to weighty situations, and to the extent that we accept these situations to be definitive of the human condition, people will have responded ritually to structurally similar weighty situations in earlier times too—recurrently so. As a result, one can expect archetypal narratives *and* archetypal rites to have gradually developed in response to these types of weighty situations and to have made it into humankind's cultural archive—whether conceived of in the plural or singular. When people are confronted with the same situation anew, they can readily resort to them. They enact a rite and become protagonists in the process. They enact a rite and become characters, subject to the instructions lodged in an “immemorial” ritual script *and* the intentions that it imposes on them (Humphrey and Laidlaw 1994: 237).

One widely acknowledged feature of ritual activity is that it tends to strip situations of their empirical detail. Part of this is surely that ritual action is typically more formal than non-ritual action (Rappaport 1999: 33–34) and that formalization implies, by definition, the reduction of empirical detail. If you address people informally by first name, the variation is nearly endless. If you address those same people more formally, the variation is reduced to two or three: sir, ma'am or miss. But part of it is also that ritual action, to the extent that it re-presents everyday activity—our actual responses to weighty situations—, tends to offer a stylized, a pared-down model of that actual activity. Humphrey and Laidlaw (1994: 146) illustrate this dynamic with reference to an agricultural rite in which

[a] person, dressed in a tinsel crown, takes just a token spadeful from a marked off square of earth. Ritualization has stripped away most of the untidy activity of gardening, and this leaves a pared-down act, which is more suitable to carry a special meaning [in Frye's terms: archetypal significance]; but at the same time it has removed the clues to everyday understanding. Now we are not at all sure what is going on. Thus, although ritualized digging-sowing is not random as regards representing “fertility” [...], it is not directly readable either.

In this view, to ritualize is to stylize. It is to pare down and to rid human experiences of empirical contingency. It is also, as the above fragment suggests strongly, to rid human activ-

ities of their practical purposes. This process of paring down is what makes ritual activity recognizable as ritual activity. This process of paring down is also what gives to ritual activity its archetypal flavor. Particular situations lose their particularity by re-presenting them as instances of a more general condition. I do not want to speculate about whether this was the intention of our ritualizing ancestors, and neither do I want to suggest that our ritualizing contemporaries take recourse to ritual action *in order to* embellish their particular situations with archetypal significance. As before: they might, they might not. I will suggest, however that it is a common effect of ritual action to universalize the particular situation being ritualized. For instance: an encounter with an identifiable stranger, when ritualized, becomes an encounter with a Stranger, and can plausibly be said to become more manageable as a result, even if only for the duration of the rite. This universalization of particular situations is an effect of ritual action that the literature on ritual in world politics has rarely noted (compare Mälksoo 2026: Table 1). I consider it one of the main theoretical benefits of the notion of ritual protagonism to bring this effect to the fore.

Willy Brandt's Genuflection: An Instrumental and Non-Instrumental Interpretation

Let me briefly discuss the example of the the *Kniefall von Warschau*. Willy Brandt's genuflection before the Memorial of the 1943 Warsaw Ghetto Uprising has been interpreted many times before as an arresting gesture that helped the German chancellor to consolidate his *Ostpolitik* (Rauer 2006: 268–274; see also Wilson and Bleiker 2014; Noyes and Wille 2025: 23), as a gesture that supported his pursuit of a “politics of peace” (Goedde 2019) by signaling that Germany was willing to reckon with its violent past (Engert 2014). I do not wish to dispute this overall interpretation but rather wish to show how—in tune with the distinction between intended effects and side-effects—the interpretation is compatible with an instrumental and non-instrumental understanding of ritual action, and how a instrumental and non-instrumental interpretation read the precise significance of the event meaningfully differently. In light of the dominance of the instrumental understanding of ritual action in our field, I emphasize the interpretive limits of casting Willy Brandt as a ritual agent and highlight the value-added of presenting him as a ritual protagonist.

The Context of Willy Brandt's Genuflection

When Willy Brandt sank to his knees before the Warsaw Memorial on December 7, 1970, he held the office of chancellor of the Federal Republic of Germany. He had started his executive political career a solid decade earlier, having been elected the mayor of West Berlin in 1957, a position that he would hold until 1966, when he became the Minister of Foreign Affairs and vice-chancellor of the FRG and ultimately, in 1969, its chancellor. During his tenure as the mayor of West Berlin, the East German authorities had the Berlin Wall built in order to prevent East Germans from escaping into West Germany. The Soviet Union had approved and the American President Kennedy readily acquiesced in this move, but it left Brandt highly dismayed. He felt that “the two superpowers had bought themselves peace at the expense of the people of Berlin” (Goedde 2019: 193). The Berlin Wall represented a form of peace that suited the balance of forces that defined the early Cold War, but Brandt thought of it as an unproductive peace, a peace not worthy of the name of peace.

Unsurprisingly, therefore, once he assumed federal office, he began to re-orient German foreign policy. In this endeavor he was aided by a propitious international context, which saw the United States slowly unfolding a policy of détente vis-à-vis the Soviet Union, which itself had for some time been proposing a future of “peaceful co-existence” (Odysseos 2007: xiii–xviii). At the same time, Brandt's re-orientation of German foreign policy was hampered domestically by the opposition of expellees—ethnic Germans expelled from Central and Eastern European states—and of more conservative politicians committed to the Hallstein doctrine which “stipulated that West Germany refused diplomatic relations with any country that recognized the East German regime” (Goedde 2019: 196). Brandt broke with that doctrine and initiated his *Ostpolitik* instead. The policy had many aspects but centered around the negotiation of a series of agreements, including the 1970 Treaty of Moscow (in which it *de facto* recognized the independent existence of the German Democratic Republic) and, that same year, a treaty normalizing the FRG's relations with Poland. In conclusion of this latter treaty, Brandt traveled to Warsaw for the official signing. During this stay he also visited the Warsaw memorial to pay his respect to the victims of the 1943 uprising in the Warsaw Ghetto. This is when he kneeled down and sat silent. The press reported on the moment in some detail (quoted in Rauer 2006: 268).

The Chancellor slowly approached the monument, he paused for a moment, adjusted the ribbons of a wreath made of white carnations, then he spontaneously sank onto his knees, as if shot dead, remaining still and stony-faced in this position. (*Corriere della Sera*, December 8, 1970)

He stepped from his car and walked slowly toward the memorial between two flame-lit stone menorahs. Mr. Brandt, who had spent the Nazi period in Scandinavia, dropped to his knees and remained that way for a full minute. He bowed his head slightly and then rose heavily. When he turned, the edge of his mouth was trembling. He joined his official party and walked slowly back, past the widely separated thin line of spectators. (*New York Times*, December 8, 1970)

Willy Brandt as Ritual Agent

If one wishes to read the events described in these fragments as an instance of ritual agency, one would have to draw attention to the fact that Willy Brandt used the platform offered by a ritual convention to enhance his diplomatic clout and make a success out of his politics of peace. One would further point out that Brandt skillfully inserted a charismatic moment by subtly deviating from the script (Noyes and Wille 2025: 26). Rather than merely bend the head, as most dignitaries would have done in the same situation, he sank down and remained still for a full minute. As Rauer (2006: 275) emphasizes in his account of the event, “[according] to the rules for the fulfillment of official scripts and systems of collective representations, the gesture presented an innovation,” and this transgressive aspect added to its impact. From within this perspective, one would then also expect a positive, practical effect. One would expect Brandt's agency to have been amplified. And this then is also what Rauer (2006: 275) maintains, not wholly without reason. He insists on the “significance of the kneefall for Brandt's *Ostpolitik*,” pointing out that “[his] performance was an indirect but nevertheless powerful way of silencing or diminishing the influence of [the] oppositional voices [of the expellees and more conservative politicians].”

While meaningful, the interpretation has its limits. For one, the concept of ritual agency presumes that ritual agents *deploy* ritual practices deliberately, that they orchestrate ritual occasions with premeditation. However, in the scholar-

ship on the *Kniefall* it is well-established that Brandt did not premeditate his gesture. As also Rauer (2006: 275) observes: “[the] gesture was spontaneous” and it was valued for its spontaneity. “Much more important for me in existential terms, infinitely more important than the Nobel Peace Prize that Brandt received in 1971,” recollected Gumbrecht (2013: 175) in his book *After 1945*, “was the question whether his genuflection in the Warsaw ghetto was spontaneous, or whether it was a calculated gesture [. . .].” Gumbrecht and his peers hoped it to be a spontaneous gesture, because that would imply sincerity on Brandt’s part, and widely agreed that it was. Now, the spontaneity of the gesture may have added to the perception of Willy Brandt’s performance as “authentic” and this may well have added to the amplification of his agency in the way that the concept of ritual agency predicts, but to the extent that it falsifies its assumption about the instrumental nature of ritual action, and hints at ritual instinct instead, it nonetheless sits ill with that understanding of ritual action. Brandt’s gesture may have silenced his opponents, but this does not appear to have been Brandt’s intention with the gesture and may more meaningfully be thought of as what Staal (1979: 11) considered a “side-effect” of ritual: causally consequential (as all things that happen in the world are somehow causally consequential), but not fully grasping the significance of what was unfolding.

One could obviously counter that Brandt’s intention was not to silence his opponents but to further his *Ostpolitik*. However, in addition to the issue of the spontaneous character of the gesture (and thus the apparent absence of instrumental intention), this argument runs into the problem that the chronology does not work. When Willy Brandt fell to his knees, the policy of rapprochement with Central and East European states had already been put in place. The Treaty of Moscow had been negotiated and signed. The treaty normalizing the FRG’s relations with Poland had also been negotiated and would in any case be signed during Brandt’s visit. For ritual action to have a consequential causal impact, in line with the concept of ritual agency, it should precede the effect that it is hoped to accomplish, not come after the effect has already been secured. If agency of any kind was involved in the process, as inevitably it does, it appears to have been the discursive agency of Willy Brandt propagating his politics of peace and the pragmatic agency of his advisor Egon Bahr, including secret negotiations with the Soviet Union (Goedde 2019: 217). If ritual agency of some sort was involved in the process, it would have had to have been at an earlier stage. Brandt’s meeting with Willi Stoph in the spring of 1970 in the East German city of Erfurt might count, as it included acrimonious procession through Erfurt’s streets (Goedde 2019: 217). But his genuflection in Warsaw does not properly fit the model and cannot, with regard to furthering Brandt’s *Ostpolitik*, claim the causal significance that the model would lead one to fancy. As also Noyes and Wille (2025: 23) acknowledge, Brandt’s *Kniefall* had “limited direct consequences.”

Willy Brandt as Ritual Protagonist

Compare now an interpretation of Willy Brandt as a ritual protagonist. It should first be remembered that the concept of ritual protagonism entertains the assumption that ritual action is non-instrumental in nature and takes this non-instrumentality of ritual action to extend to the level of the individual ritual participant. Ritual participants do not necessarily intend to gain from the ritual enactment, be it in terms of material benefit or in terms of cultural capital. In this regard, it is significant that Willy Brandt did not have to seek personal redemption or forgiveness for the atrocities that the

Warsaw memorial commemorates. Although he was now the chancellor of (one of) the successor regime(s) of Nazi Germany, he was himself free of personal guilt (Engert 2014: 103). In 1933, at the age of twenty, Brandt had fled to Norway to avoid political persecution by the Nazi party. When Nazi Germany subsequently occupied Norway, he sought refuge in Sweden and helped organize the Norwegian resistance from there. This absence of personal guilt, and thus also the absence of the pursuit of personal redemption, accords with the concept of ritual protagonism. It does not establish the validity of the concept, but it does give plausibility to the attempt to develop an interpretation in these terms.

Such an interpretation would observe that the genuflection did not obviously constitute an “innovation,” in spite of Rauer’s (2006: 275) claim to the contrary. The introduction of the gesture can equally be thought of as a process of embedding, as an instance of one well-established rite (of penance) being embedded within another well-established rite (of commemoration) (Chung 2017: 129–139). After all, rites of penance have a venerated history, certainly in the Christian tradition, and they have historically been a staple feature of peacemaking processes too, at least in the Christian world (Engert 2014: 97). Katherine Ludwig Jansen (2018) has documented this in detail for medieval times. She shows how in medieval Italian communes, where both conflict and peacemaking was rife, ritual penance stood on a par with the ritual exchange of a kiss as a gesture of peace. In the words of one thirteenth-century Franciscan preacher: “Just as enemies are accustomed to kiss each other when they meet to make peace, likewise this sinner [Mary Magdalen] who had waged war on the Lord, now came to make peace and gave kisses to his feet” (quoted in Jansen 2018: xix). Admittedly, rites of penance had lost their public prominence by the time that Willy Brandt knelt down in Warsaw, but the very spontaneity of his gesture attests to the fact that the practice was still available in a shared cultural archive. Willy Brandt may therefore be said not to have innovated but to have resuscitated a ritual practice. To the extent that he did so spontaneously, it must have made intuitive sense to him to resuscitate this particular gesture. It corresponded to the predicament—of not merely having fought an enemy, but of having sinned thoroughly while fighting the enemy to extermination—that he understood Germans to be confronted with after the war.

Further elaborating on the interpretation, one could point at the pared-down character of Brandt’s gesture. It did not involve any words, let alone an elaborate speech. This was a feature of the occasion that was emphasized in contemporary reporting (Chung 2017: 131–132) and that Brandt himself singled out too. Writing in his memoir, he explained that “he had only done what humans do when words fail” (quoted in Chung 2017: 130). Brandt did not do more than sink to his knees and remain in silence for about a minute. Paring down a request for forgiveness to such an extent, without the direct presence of those one is asking forgiveness from, has the major consequence that one erases contingency from the act. The act ceases to be an action that is directed to others. It becomes a pure gesture. It becomes precisely what Frits Staal calls perfect activity: a perfect request for penance, an unsullied expression of the desire for forgiveness and peace.

Crucially, the pared-down character of the *Kniefall*, in addition to being unsullied, has the further effect of rendering the moment archetypal. Although Valentin Rauer (2006: 263–267) is certainly right to claim that Brandt’s speechless gesture defines the moment in time when the German nation may be said to have finally assumed collective responsibility for the transgressions of the Nazi regime (but see Engert

2014), it is also the case that the gesture, because of its utterly abstract and therefore universal nature, simultaneously opened space for an interpretation that related what had happened not to German unicity but to a conception of original and therefore universal sin. Martin Chung (2017: 138) quotes a Greek informant, reflecting on Nazi atrocities in the wake of and in response to Brandt's genuflection, who pondered reflectively that "[. . .] war is war: [a situation] in which human beings are under other laws." The ritual of penance performed in the most stylized, the most universal of manners, the acts being repented for achieved universal meaning too. They were integrated in a world of mythical recurrence.

Conclusion

The history of ritual theory offers a rich archive full of fruitful disagreements. This implies that when we import the notion of ritual into our field, we should do so in sufficient awareness of this copious-yet-contested history. We should indulge in its richness. However, when I read the rapidly growing literature on ritual in world politics, I am often struck by its relatively narrow instrumental conception of ritual action. As I have tried to show in the introduction to this paper, scholars tend more or less explicitly to analyze ritual as a "useful resource," which is also, in my reading, the core idea in Maria Mälksoo's framing article for the current special issue. We appear to be shy to indulge in the rich history of ritual theory and stick with those approaches that resonate with common conceptions of political actors as political *agents* that pursue their political projects with whatever means available, now including ritual means.

Drawing inspiration from a number of important contributions to the debates on the nature of ritual action in anthropology and social theory, I have sought to unsettle the self-evidence of this instrumental interpretation of ritual action. The entailments of the conceptualization of *ritual as instrument* sit uncomfortably with the (well-established-but-neither-uncontested) ideas of (i) the auto-telicity of ritual action (Staal), of (ii) universal participation in ritual practices (Rappaport), and of (iii) humankind's ritual instinct (Wittgenstein). What is more, building on these ideas, it was possible to develop a coherent, non-instrumental interpretation of ritual action. In this alternative approach, political actors do not appear as agents but as *protagonists* (Frye). Confronted with weighty situations, they are prone to ritualize those situations: to re-present them by way of a set of pared-down acts and/or utterances. As they go through these motions, but only for the duration of the rite, both they and the situation lose their empirical specificity. The ritual actors become archetypal characters and the situation that they found themselves confronted with achieves universal significance. Crucially, this non-instrumental interpretation of ritual action does not presume that ritual activity has much causal impact on subsequent developments. It does not presume that actors who resort to ritual activity will have their agency amplified, that they will be able to achieve mastery over others or their environment. If anything, as ritual protagonists enact rites that they feel to have archetypal significance, that they feel to capture an aspect of the human condition that probably cannot be overcome, this process of ritual universalization is more likely to attune world-political actors to the limits of political agency. Was not Willy Brandt's *Kniefall* also a reflection on Nazi Germany's presumption of mastery and the harm it had caused?

Funding

Research for this article benefited from a grant of the Research Foundation—Flanders (FWO) (Grant number: G015824N). The open access publication of the Special Forum this article is part of has been supported by the ERC Consolidator Grant RITUAL DETERRENCE, project number 101043468.

References

- AALBERTS, TANJA, XYMENA KUROWSKA, ANNA LEANDER, MARIA MÄLKSOO, CHARLOTTE HEATH-KELLY, LUISA LOBATO, AND TED SVENSSON. 2020. "Rituals of World Politics: On (Visual) Practices Disordering Things." *Critical Studies on Security* 8: 240–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21624887.2020.1792734>.
- ACKERMAN, ROBERT. 1975. "Frazer on Myth and Ritual." *Journal of the History of Ideas* 36: 115–34. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2709014>.
- ALEXANDER, JEFFREY. 2004. "Cultural Pragmatics: Social Performance between Ritual and Strategy." *Sociological Theory* 22: 527–73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0735-2751.2004.00233.x>.
- AUGUSTINE, SAINT. 2013. *The City of God against the Pagans*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- BAELE, STÉPHANE, AND THIERRY BALZACQ. 2022. "International Rituals: An Analytical Framework and Its Theoretical Repertoires." *Review of International Studies* 48: 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210521000401>.
- BAMBERG, MICHAEL. 2022. "Positioning the Subject: Agency between Master and Counter. 25–41 in Saša Bosančić." In *Positioning the Subject: Methodologien der Subjektivierungsforschung / Methodologies of Subjectivation Research*, edited by F. Brodersen, L. Pfahl, L. Schürmann, T. Spies and B. Traue Wiesbaden: Springer.
- BARKAWI, TARAK. 2017. *Soldiers of Empire: Indian and British Armies in World War II*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316718612>.
- BARTOLINI, STEFANO. 2018. *The Political*. Colchester: ECPR Press.
- BAYNE, TIM. 2008. "The Phenomenology of Agency." *Philosophy Compass* 3: 182–202. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-9991.2007.00122.x>.
- BELL, CATHERINE. 1992. *Ritual Theory, Ritual Practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- BELLAH, ROBERT. 2005. "Durkheim and Ritual." In: *The Cambridge Companion to Durkheim*, edited by J. Alexander and P. Smith, 183–210. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CCOL9780521806725>.
- BETTIZA, GREGORIO, AND DAVID LEWIS. 2020. "Authoritarian Powers and Norm Contestation in the Liberal International Order: Theorizing the Politics of Ideas and Identity." *Journal of Global Security Studies* 5: 559–77. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jogss/ogz075>.
- CAMPT, TINA MARIE. 2019. "Black Visuality and the Practice of Refusal." *Women & Performance: A Journal of Feminist Theory* 29: 79–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0740770X.2019.1578625>.
- CHOWDHURY, ARJUN, AND RAYMOND DUVALL. 2011. "Practices of Theory." In *International Practices*, edited by E. Adler and V. Pouliot, 335–54. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- CHUNG, C.K. MARTIN. 2017. *Repentance for the Holocaust: Lessons from Jewish Thought for Confronting the German Past*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- CSIKSZENTMIHALYI, MIHALY, AND NINA GILBERT. 1995. "Singing and the Self: Choral Music as 'Active Leisure'." *The Choral Journal* 35: 13–9.
- DE LARA, PHILIPPE. 2003. "Wittgenstein as Anthropologist: the Concept of Ritual Instinct." *Philosophical Investigations* 26: 109–24. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9205.00190>.
- ENGERT, STEFAN. 2014. "Confessing the Holocaust: The Evolution of German Guilt." In *On the Uses and Abuses of Political Apologies*, edited by M. Mihai and M. Thaler, 96–114. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- EPSTEIN, CHARLOTTE, THOMAS LINDEMANN, AND OLE JACOB SENDING. 2018. "Frustrated Sovereigns: The Agency that Makes the World Go Around." *Review of International Studies* 44: 787–804. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210518000402>.
- FARNETH, MOLLY. 2023. *The Politics of Ritual*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- FRYE, NORTHROP. 1951. "The Archetypes of Literature." *The Kenyon Review* 13: 92–110.

- GOEDDE, PETRA. 2019. *The Politics of Peace: A Global Cold War History*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780195370836.001.0001>.
- GUMBRECHT, HANS ULRICH. 2013. *After 1945: Latency as Origin of the Present*. Redwood City: Stanford University Press.
- HABERMAS, JÜRGEN. 2007. "The Language Game of Responsible Agency and the Problem of Free Will: How Can Epistemic Dualism be Reconciled with Ontological Monism?" *Philosophical Explorations* 10: 13–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13869790601170128>.
- HILLEWAERT, SARAH. 2016. "Tactics and Tactility: A Sensory Semiotics of Handshakes in Coastal Kenya." *American Anthropologist* 118: 49–66. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.12517>.
- A. HORVATH, B. THOMASSEN, AND H. WYDRA (eds.). 2015. *Breaking Boundaries: Varieties of Liminality*. New York: Berghahn Books. <https://doi.org/10.3167/9781782387664>.
- HUMPREY, CAROLINE, AND JAMES LAIDLAW. 1994. *The Archetypes of Ritual Action: A Theory of Ritual Illustrated by the Jain Rite of Worship*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198277880.001.0001>.
- JANSEN, KATHERINE LUDWIG. 2018. *Peace and Penance in Late Medieval Italy*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- KESSLER, OLIVER. 2016. "The Contingency of Constructivism: On Norms, the Social, and the Third." *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* 45: 43–63. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305829816655879>.
- KNOTTER, LUCAS. 2021. "Why Declare Independence? Observing, Believing, and Performing the Ritual." *Review of International Studies* 47: 252–71. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210520000443>.
- KOSCHUT, SIMON. 2024. "When International Rituals Go Wrong: How Ritual Failure Undermines Peaceful Change in NATO." *Cooperation and Conflict* 59: 290–307. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00108367231184731>.
- KUSTERMANS, JORG, TED SVENSSON, JULIA COSTA LOPEZ, TRACEY BLASENHEIM, AND ALVINA HOFFMANN. 2022. "Ritual and Authority in World Politics." *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 35: 2–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09557571.2021.1975647>.
- KUSTERMANS, JORG. 2021. "Gift-giving in Byzantine Diplomacy." *The Hague journal of diplomacy*. 16: 155–65. <https://doi.org/10.1163/1871191X-BJA10.057>.
- LOPEZ FRIAS, FRANCISCO JAVIER. 2020. "Does Play Constitute the Good Life? Suits and Aristotle on Autotelicity and Living Well." *Journal of the Philosophy of Sport* 47: 168–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00948705.2020.1745076>.
- MACINTYRE, ALASDAIR. 2007. *After Virtue: A Study in Moral Theory, Third Edition*. Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame Press.
- MÄLKSOO, MARIA. 2012. "The Challenge of Liminality for International Relations Theory." *Review of International Studies* 38: 481–94. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210511000829>.
- MÄLKSOO, MARIA. 2026. "The Logic of Ritual Action in International Relations." *Global Studies Quarterly*
- MCNEILL, WILLIAM. 1996. *Keeping Together in Time: Dance and Drill in Human History*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- NEUMANN, IVER. 2021. "Diplomatic Gifts as Ordering Devices." *The Hague Journal of Diplomacy* 16: 186–94. <https://doi.org/10.1163/1871191X-BJA10061>.
- NOYES, DOROTHY, AND TOBIAS WILLE. 2025. "From Performance to Uptake: A Process Model of Exemplarity." In *Exemplarity in Global Politics*, edited by D. Noyes and T. Wille, 23–46. Bristol: Bristol University Press
- ODYSSEOS, LOUIZA. 2007. *The Subject of Coexistence: Otherness in International Relations*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- OREN, IDO, AND TY SOLOMON. 2015. "WMD, WMD, WMD: Securitisation through Ritualised Incantation of Ambiguous Phrases." *Review of International Studies* 41: 313–36. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210514000205>.
- OTTO, ADELHEID. 2015. "Defining and Transgressing the Boundaries between Ritual Commensality and Daily Commensal Practices: the Case of Late Bronze Age Tall Bazi." In *Between Feasts and Daily Meals*, edited by S. Pollock, 205–23. Edition Topoi.
- QUACK, JOHANNES. 2010. "Bell, Bourdieu and Wittgenstein on Ritual Sense." In *The Problem of Ritual Efficacy*, edited by W. Sax, J. Quack and J. Weinholt, 169–88. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195394405.001.0001>.
- RAPPAPORT, ROY. 1999. *Ritual and Religion in the Making of Humanity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511814686>.
- RAUER, VALENTIN. 2006. "Symbols in Action: Willy Brandt's Kneefall at the Warsaw Memorial." In *Social Performance: Symbolic Action, Cultural Pragmatics and Ritual*, edited by J. Alexander, B. Giesen and J. Mast, 257–82. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511616839>.
- ROBB, JOHN. 2010. "Beyond Agency." *World Archaeology* 42: 493–520. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.2010.520856>.
- ROBBINS, JOEL. 2016. "Ritual Pluralism and Value Pluralism: Why One Ritual is Never Enough." *Suomen Antropologi* 41: 6–13.
- RUMELILI, BAHAR. 2012. "Liminal Identities and Processes of Domestication and Subversion in International Relations." *Review of International Studies* 38: 495–508. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210511000830>.
- SCHATZKI, THEODORE. 2010. *The Timespace of Human Activity: on Performance, Society, and History as Indeterminate Teleological Events*. Lanham: Lexington Books.
- SCHATZKI, THEODORE. 2025. "Agency." *Information and Organization* 35: 100553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infoandorg.2024.100553>.
- SCHUTZ, ALFRED. 1962. *Collected Papers: Vol. I: the Problem of Social Reality*. Leiden: Martinus Nijhoff.
- STAAL, FRITS. 1979. "The Meaninglessness of Ritual." *Numen* 26: 2–22. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156852779X00244>.
- SWIDLER, ANN. 1986. "Culture in Action: Symbols and Strategies." *American Sociological Review* 51: 273–86. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095521>.
- THOMASSEN, BJÖRN. 2009. "The Uses and Meaning of Liminality." *International Political Anthropology* 2: 5–28.
- TURNER, VICTOR. 1979. *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-Structure*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- VAN GENNEP, ARNOLD. 1909. *Les Rites De Passage*. Paris: Emile Nourry.
- VON BILLERBECK, SARAH. 2020. "Mirror, Mirror on the Wall": Self-Legitimation by International Organizations." *International Studies Quarterly* 64: 207–19. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isq/sqz089>.
- WEGNER, NICOLE. 2021. "Ritual, Rhythms, and the Discomforting Endurance of Militarism: Affective Methodologies and Ethico-Political Challenges." *Global Studies Quarterly* 1: 1–10.
- WILSON, ERIN, AND ROLAND BLEIKER. 2014. "Performing Political Apologies." In *Memory and Trauma in International Relations: Theories, Cases and Debates*, edited by E. Resende and D. Budryte, 42–56. London: Routledge.
- WITTGENSTEIN, LUDWIG. 2018. *The Mythology in Our Language: Remarks on Frazer's Golden Bough*. Chicago: HAU Books.
- WONG, SEANON. 2021. "One-Upmanship and Putdowns: The Aggressive Use of Interaction Rituals in Face-to-Face Diplomacy." *International Theory* 13: 341–71. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1752971920000196>.
- ZIJDERVELD, ANTON. 1972. "The Problem of Adequacy: Reflections on Alfred Schutz's Contribution to the Methodology of the Social Sciences." *European Journal of Sociology*. 15: 176–90. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003975600002484>.